

SOME THOUGHTS ON THE INTERNATIONAL LEGAL BASIS FOR PREVENTION AND EXPOSURE OF FRAUD

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14858978>

Abstract. The article analyzes the international legal framework for the prevention and exposure of fraud, and develops scientifically based proposals and recommendations.

Keywords: declaration, agreement, treaty, international documents.

To date, the Republic of Uzbekistan has succeeded in adopting over one hundred international documents with more than forty countries and influential international organizations. The content of these international documents also addresses issues of combating property crimes. In particular, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights states: "Everyone has the right to own property alone as well as in association with others" (Article 17) [1]; The "Cooperation Agreement" between the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Latvia identifies one of the areas of cooperation as the fight against property crimes, the search for criminals, persons evading investigation and trial, and those avoiding serving sentences (Article 1); the implementation of operational-search measures and procedural actions (Article 2) [2]; In the Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Government of Ukraine "On Cooperation in Combating Crime," one of the areas of cooperation is crimes against property (Article 2); as a form of cooperation, the exchange of information of interest about crimes being prepared or committed, as well as about individuals, legal entities and organizations involved in them; the execution of requests for conducting operational-search activities (Article 3) [3]; In the Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Government of the Russian Federation "On Cooperation in Combating Crime," one of the areas of cooperation is crimes against property (Article 2); one of the forms of cooperation is the mutual exchange of information of interest about prepared or committed crimes and individuals, legal entities and organizations related to them; execution of requests for conducting operational-search measures; apprehension of persons evading criminal investigation or serving a sentence (Article 3) [4];

In the Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Government of the Republic of Georgia "On Cooperation in Combating Crime," one of the areas of cooperation is the study of crimes against personal property (Article 2); one of the forms of cooperation is the exchange of information of interest about prepared or committed crimes and individuals and legal entities and organizations related to them; execution of requests for conducting operational-search measures; identification of the hiding place of persons hiding from criminal investigation or serving a sentence (Article 3) [5]; In the Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Government of the Federal Republic of Germany "On Cooperation in Combating Organized Crime, Terrorism and Other Dangerous Crimes" on combating property and property crimes (Article 3) [6]; Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan

"On Cooperation in Combating Crime" on crimes against property (Article 2); mutual exchange of information of interest about crimes being prepared or committed and individuals and legal entities, organizations related to them; execution of requests for conducting operational-search measures; detention of persons evading criminal prosecution or serving a sentence (Article 3) [7]; Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Government of the Republic of Bulgaria "On Cooperation in Combating Crime" on organized crime (Article 2); exchange of information that may be useful for solving, preventing, and investigating crimes (Article 3) [8]; The Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Government of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On Cooperation in Combating Crime" provides for the exchange of information that contributes to the detection, prevention, and disclosure of crimes; execution of requests for the implementation of operational-search measures (Article 3) [9]; Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Government of the Kyrgyz Republic "On Cooperation in Combating Crime" on crimes against human property (Article 2); exchange of information of interest about crimes being prepared or committed, as well as about individuals and legal entities and organizations involved in them; execution of requests for conducting operational-search measures; search for persons hiding from criminal prosecution or serving a sentence (Article 3) [10]; The Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Federal Government of the Austrian Republic "On Cooperation in the Field of Security and Combating Crime" defines such provisions as the exchange of information for the purpose of solving and investigating crimes and eliminating crimes that pose a great threat to public safety; determining the methods of committing crimes by organized groups, their composition, structure, scope of activity, and criminal connections (Article 3) [11]. Bilateral and multilateral international agreements have also been signed with developed countries such as Moldova, Kuwait, Kyrgyzstan, Belarus, Turkmenistan, the UAE, Saudi Arabia, and Kazakhstan on combating crime and cooperation, and general attention is being paid to these two important issues. For example, when analyzing the essence of these international documents, it can be seen that a rule has been established to combat crimes of a common property type. In the "List of Information Submitted to the Interstate Information Bank," approved by the Agreement "On the Exchange of Information in the Field of Combating Crime" (signed in Astana on May 22, 2009), it was revealed during the study that information about unsolved crimes includes a clause on the commission of large and especially large-scale fraud, and other international documents do not contain such provisions.

Over the past 5 years (2019-2024), cases of fraud have been increasing in our republic. For example, in 2023, the majority of criminal cases considered by the courts were related to fraud[12].

Today, there is an increase in cases of skilled fraudsters using digital technologies to illegally appropriate funds by issuing online loans in citizens' names through mobile applications of commercial banks and transferring loan funds deposited into bank cards. In 2024, in 615 cases, material damage amounting to about 20 billion soums was caused by fraudulently allocating online loans in citizens' names[13]. Most of the perpetrators are located in other countries and are carrying out their criminal plans using cyberspace.

To find a solution to this problem, it is first necessary to strengthen the international legal framework for combating fraud. Specifically, it is proposed to include the following provision

as a form of cooperation in international documents adopted on combating crime and cooperation: "identifying persons who have committed fraud through various methods and exposing their actions."

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